

Exploitation, Sustainability & Business Plans v3

WP8 - Dissemination, sustainability and exploitation

Version: 1.00

SPHINX

A Universal Cyber Security Toolkit for
Health-Care Industry

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Executive Summary

This is the final version of the SPHINX “Exploitation, Sustainability & Business Plans” document. The first and the second version (“D8.4. Exploitation, Sustainability & Business Plans v1” and “D8.7. Exploitation, Sustainability & Business Plans v2” respectively) that were submitted on M12 and on M24 presented the SPHINX project outputs, the overall exploitation plan that the entire consortium follows and the exploitation KPIs that should be reached by the end of the project and onwards. This version aims to present a consolidated view of the SPHINX exploitation options, as they were defined by the Consortium during the final stages of the project, elaborate on the strategy for the commercialisation of the SPHINX Toolkit and conclude on the key takeaways for the successful uptake of SPHINX and its main outputs once the project is completed.

Overall, SPHINX resulted in 5 essential results that can be sustained and exploited:

- the **SPHINX Toolkit** that is the main tangible output of the project, and
- the **SPHINX individual components** that the SPHINX Toolkit is composed of,
- the **pilot cases** success stories,
- the policy recommendations and **best practices** from the implementation of SPHINX platform in replicated real environments, and
- the **scientific knowledge** that was generated through the different research and development activities.

The current deliverable elaborates on the essential exploitation options related to each of the afore-listed result. It evaluates what was achieved throughout the project duration and which can be the future steps towards a successful continuation and advancement of these results. It analyses insights from project partners regarding their potential exploitation of their outputs and drafts a business plan outlining the necessary actions to bring SPHINX Toolkit to the market following a viable plan. The deliverable also comments on the partners future activities that can ensure the further uptake of SPHINX once the project ends.

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1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose & Scope

This report is the third and final version of the SPHINX **Exploitation, Sustainability and Business Plan** and incorporates all actions involved in setting up the environment for further exploitation of the SPHINX outputs. The report is the main outcome of “Task 8.3: Exploitation, Sustainability & Business Plans”.

In this context, this report aims to:

- Present the key SPHINX exploitable results focusing on the exploitation actions implemented for each result.
- Identify the business cases for exploitation.
- Define the sustainability plan that the consortium will follow to sustain the project outputs, beyond the end of the project.

This document follows the deployment of SPHINX Toolkit in the pilot sites and focuses on the identification and validation of the SPHINX value proposition and the development of the SPHINX business models and business plan to stimulate the commercialisation prospects of the SPHINX Toolkit. What is more, it enlists important exploitation achievements, as those have been attained through the various dissemination and exploitation activities and paves the ground for future actions that will ensure the sustainability of project’s outputs.

1.2 Structure of the deliverable

The document begins with a presentation of the SPHINX main exploitable results (Chapter 2) and provides a summary of the main exploitation achievements (Chapter 4). It continues with an analysis of the SPHINX partners key exploitation and sustainability options (Chapter 4). Then, the deliverable discusses the SPHINX business model (Chapter 5) while the plan for realising the commercial exploitation of SPHINX is presented in Chapter 6. The deliverable continues (Chapter 7) with a proposal for the development of a cybersecurity in healthcare working group that will consist of SPHINX partners and will work towards the exploitation and sustainability of the project’s results. Finally, the sustainability aspect is addressed in Chapter 8.

1.3 Relation to other WPs & Tasks

This report is the final outcome of “Task 8.3: Exploitation, Sustainability & Business Plans”, which is a horizontal action across all SPHINX Work Packages. In particular, within WP8 Dissemination, sustainability and exploitation, all tasks are complementary. It is also closely connected with the different tasks related to IPRs (“Task 7.4 Legal analysis evaluation of the SPHINX use cases and business model”, “Task 8.5 Knowledge Management and IPR Protection”). Furthermore, this task aligns with the WPs (WP2,3,4,5,6) which are related to the identification of requirements and architecture and the development of the SPHINX components and Toolkit and therefore, the exploitation plan should be updated according to the developed project results. Finally, Task 8.3 is also aligned to “WP7 Technology Validation Pilots and Privacy assessment”, because it is focusing on the implementation of SPHINX Toolkit in replicated/emulated settings of real environments which impacts the exploitation of the results. In that respect, the exploitation needs to have an overall understanding of the different work that is being implemented in all SPHINX work packages and tasks.

2 SPHINX Exploitable Results

In this section we briefly present the key exploitable results of SPHINX project. These are the projects' results that have been developed within the project's lifetime and could be exploited after the end of the project. A more detailed description of the key exploitable outputs is presented in the previous versions of this deliverable. SPHINX exploitable outputs are the following:

- SPHINX Toolkit
- SPHINX individual components (20 individual components)
- SPHINX pilots
- SPHINX policy recommendations and best practices
- Scientific and technical knowledge

Figure 1: SPHINX key exploitable results

SPHINX Toolkit

The main exploitable output of SPHINX project is the **SPHINX Toolkit**. For the SPHINX Toolkit, this exploitation and sustainability plan focuses on developing the SPHINX business model ([Chapter 5](#)) and the SPHINX business plan ([Chapter 6](#)). The SPHINX market analysis was also presented in “D8.9 Market analysis” that was delivered on M36 of the project.

SPHINX components

The SPHINX Toolkit comprises of **individual components** that are interoperable and reusable, adhering to commonly accepted best practices of object-oriented software design flow. For these individual components, this exploitation and sustainability plan focuses on presenting the actions that have been implemented by the consortium with regards to exploiting and sustaining these components (together with the scientific and technical knowledge that was generated) even after the end of the project. These actions are presented in detail in [Sub-chapter 3.1](#) of the current document.

SPHINX pilots

Strong demonstration (WP7) of the SPHINX platform took place at four pilot sites (General Hospital of Volos (Greece), University Hospital of Larissa (Greece), Hospital do Espírito Santo de Évora (Portugal), and POLARIS Medical Hospital (Romania). These demonstrations resulted to valuable knowledge, including; the **success stories**, and the **replication guidelines** that external Health Delivery Organisations could follow to deploy the SPHINX platform. The results of the pilot activities are presented in detail in “D7.5 Real-life pilot demonstrators results and consolidation including stakeholders experience evaluation and cost assessment” that was delivered in M39 of the SPHINX project. The exploitation actions for the pilot activities are presented in [Sub-chapter 3.2](#) of the current document.

Policy recommendations / best practices

SPHINX project sought to positively influence policy-making sector towards fostering a more well-rounded cybersecurity framework in healthcare via research-backed recommendations and best practices. Detailed description towards the exploitation actions implemented by the consortium with regards to policy outreach are presented in [Sub-chapter 3.3](#) of the current document.

Scientific and technical knowledge

Finally, several **scientific papers** with open access are available, allowing the maximum outreach and exploitation potential of the scientific and technical project knowledge. This action is mostly linked with “Task 8.1 Dissemination activities” and the results are briefly presented in [Sub-chapter 3.4](#).

3 Exploitation Achievements

3.1 SPHINX individual components

The SPHINX Toolkit has a modular architecture that is composed of five building blocks and **twenty key components** that are being developed by eleven technical partners.

Figure 2: SPHINX architecture

The SPHINX main building blocks are:

- **Device Verification and Certification Module,**
- **Automated Cyber Security Risk Assessment Module,**
- **Cyber Security Toolkit Module,**
- **Decision Support System and Interactive Dashboard,**
- **Third-party APIs.**

These modules are then detailed into a set of **twenty key components** that are interoperable and reusable, adhering to commonly accepted best practices of object-oriented software design. In the table below we present all the components, grouped by lead developer, the SPHINX deliverables that someone are related to these components, the current Technology Readiness Level (TRL) of the components and the main actions implemented in terms of **Dissemination and Exploitation**.

Overall, all SPHINX partners implemented a significant number of exploitation actions to ensure that both the knowledge generated during the project will remain (publicly accessible) and that appropriate actions are made to explore the sustainability (and commercialization) potential of some important components even after the project ends.

Vulnerability Assessment as a Service (VAaaS)	Hellenic Mediterranean University	5	D3.3 (M18) D3.9 (M30)			
Cybersecurity Toolbox		4	D5.5 (M22) D5.10 (M34)			
Decision Support System (DSS)	Konnekt-able Technologies	5	D5.1 (M22) D5.6 (M34)			
Analytics Engine (AE)		5	D5.1 (M22) D5.6 (M34)			
Blockchain-based Threat Registry Platform (BBTR)	Tecnalía	5	D4.3 (M20) M4.9 (M32)			
Machine Learning-empowered Intrusion Detection using Honeypot's data (MLID)	AiDEAS	5	D3.4 (M18) D3.10 (M30)			
Artificial Intelligence (AI) Honeypots	Future Intelligence	5	D4.4 (M20) D4.10 (M32)			
Cybersecurity Knowledge Base (KB)		4	D5.5 (M22) D5.10 (M34)			
Homomorphic Encryption (HE)	Tech Inspire	5	D4.6 (M20) D4.12 (M32)			
Data Traffic Monitoring (DTM)	SIMAVI	5	D4.1 (M20) D4.7 (M32)			

Anomaly Detection (AD)		5	D4.1 (M20) D4.7 (M32)			
Interactive Dashboards (ID)		5	D5.2 (M22) D5.7 (M34)			
Real-time Cyber Risk Assessment (RCRA)	National Technical University of Athens	5	D3.1 (M18) D3.7 (M30)			
Forensic Data Collection Engine (FDCE)		3	D3.1 (M18) D3.7 (M30)			
Attack and Behaviour Simulators (ABS)		3	D5.3, D5.4 (M22) D5.7, D5.8 (M34)			
Security Protocol Analysis (SPA)		2				
SPHINX API for 3rd Parties (S-API)	Edgeneering	6	D3.6 (M18) D3.12 (M30)			
Security Information and Event Management (SIEM)	Projecto Desenvolvimento Manutenção Formação e Consultadoria	6	D4.5 (M20) D4.11 (M32)			
Sandbox (SB)		4	D4.2 (M20) D4.8 (M32)			
Anonymisation and Privacy		5				
Common Integration Platform and Service Manager	INTRACOM	5	D6.1 (M16)			

Table 1: SPHINX individual components

Working on the development of the above-listed components resulted to multiple positive impacts for technical partners. As the project reaches its conclusion, partners have already pivoted the TRL of their tools and they have begun strategizing how they can leverage the expertise and resources gained through the project to enhance their offered solutions. For example, PDMFC plans to further use and advance its SIEM in-house so that it can reach a market-ready potential. Similarly, TEC and TECNALIA intent to pitch their developed components (HE and BBTR respectively) in near future in search for collaborations so that these tools can be integrated in external solutions, while INTRACOM will finetune Service Manager to deliver a solution capable of being implementing in further projects and verticals. Moreover, AiDEAS and FINT have expressed their interest for joint exploitation of their interoperable components and KT intents to further investigate the market for its own components (AE and DSS). Finally, another successful output of the SPHINX Toolkit development is identified by EDGE which notes that through SPHINX it has been able to enhance the cybersecurity capabilities of its company-owned eCare platform that is tailored for healthcare sector (patient remote monitoring).

The above outcomes were identified in the context of a 2-round exploitation survey performed within SPHINX Consortium (Appendix I and Appendix II). Further information is provided in the dedicated [Chapter 4](#).

3.2 SPHINX pilot success stories

Based on a framework established by its application scenarios and use cases, the SPHINX Toolkit was deployed and evaluated in simulated operating conditions in three pilot activities. The SPHINX pilots involved four sites:

1. the General Hospital of Volos (GHV) in Greece;
2. the University Hospital of Larissa (UHL) in Greece;
3. the Hospital do Espírito Santo de Évora (HESE) in Portugal; and
4. the Polaris Medical Hospital (POLARIS) in Romania.

Three pilots were conducted in the above sites, capturing the specifics of the SPHINX application scenarios and use cases:

Pilot Case	Pilot Sites	Application Scenario(s)
Pilot in Greece: Intra-Region Patient Data Transfer	DYPE5 GHV; DYPE5 UHL	Sharing and Exchange of Healthcare Information
Cross-Border Pilot between Greece and Romania: Cross-border Medical Data Exchange	POLARIS; DYPE5	Cross-border Healthcare Service Delivery
Pilot in Portugal: Securing Advanced Patient Care in Hospital and Homecare Environments	HESE	mHealth and Remote Patient Monitoring

Table 2: SPHINX pilot activities

Detailed information regarding the pilot schemes and their scope is presented in *D7.1 - Pilot plans including WP7 evaluation framework* that was delivered on M18 and in *D7.5 - Real-life pilot demonstrators results and consolidation including stakeholders experience evaluation and cost assessment*, that is prepared concurrently with this deliverable. What is more, key information from these two deliverables is featured at SPHINX website pages, dedicated to each pilot.

Following the pilot execution, ICT end-users from the SPHINX pilot healthcare organisations shared their perspectives regarding their involvement to the SPHINX project and the deployment of SPHINX Toolkit. Their testimonials are quoted below:

DYPE5:

“SPHINX Toolkit unifies systematically the proactive and reactive cybersecurity mechanisms.”

“The seamless collaboration with legacy security devices like firewalls enhances the cybersecurity protection level.”

“A Centralized Dashboard renders the cybersecurity protection a handy process in Healthcare Organisations.”

HESE:

“SPHINX participation was an opening to a new paradigm outside the Portuguese healthcare system in terms of cybersecurity.”

“We integrated the eCare system with SPHINX Toolkit to benefit from its set of advanced features.”

“Our expectation is that we will be able to use SPHINX tools not just with eCare, but across our entire infrastructure.”

POLARIS:

“SPHINX Toolkit brings cybersecurity tools in one common place”

“SPHINX Toolkit can afford us continuous monitoring assets and users within network”

“A centralized dashboard can ease the interactions with advanced cybersecurity processes in Healthcare Organizations”

In order to give external stakeholders the opportunity to better grasp the concepts addressed by the pilot executions, 3 videos (1 video per pilot) were created. Each video presents the process flow of the corresponding pilot case explaining the hospitals' preparation. It, also, describes the type of the attack executed and how SPHINX tools were utilised to mitigate such attack. The videos conclude with respective KPIs measured for each pilot case and with lessons learnt and testimonials from the pilot end-users who participated.

Overall, the pilot testing of SPHINX Toolkit played an essential role to maximize its potential for further uptake and sustainability, thanks to the multiple activities carried out in the context of pilot sites preparation.

In this respect, a series of 3 workshops whose scope revolved around SPHINX Toolkit's contribution to the cybersecurity of healthcare infrastructure along with raising cybersecurity awareness in hospitals' staff was organised. Namely, the workshops took place as follows:

1. [CYBERAWARE4HEALTH: Cybersecurity Awareness in Healthcare Employees](#), hosted by DYPE5 on 16 December, 2020;
2. [SPHINX4HEALTH: The SPHINX Universal Toolkit for Healthcare Organisations](#), hosted by HESE on 6 October, 2021; and
3. [SPHINX@HEALTHSECURITY: The Impact of SPHINX in Healthcare Organisations: Pilot Results](#), hosted by POLARIS on 24 February, 2022.

These workshops were targeted primarily to ICT staff of healthcare organisations, coming both from the involved project partners and external organisations, to foster cybersecurity culture via disseminating SPHINX solution and raising awareness on the integral role of cybersecurity for the resilience of contemporary health sector.

Moreover, two rounds of training sessions were performed to educate the ICT staff of the pilot sites about the SPHINX Toolkit and familiarise them with essential security aspects and how they are covered using SPHINX. Having these capacity building sessions carried out emphasized in cybersecurity's necessity in the pilot sites, thus improving SPHINX's uptake, since the pilot partners have expressed their willingness to further provide parts of their infrastructure as testbeds for further development and finetuning of SPHINX Toolkit components after project's end.

Key outcomes of these activities, also, consist of a comprehensive user manual for SPHINX Toolkit, which specifies the installation and utilization information for every component of the platform, and a Capture the Flag (CTF) challenge, that was used as a hands-on exercise to get pilot partners ready to operate SPHINX for the actual pilot cases. Such material constitutes a valuable output, that enables SPHINX partners to draft replication guidelines for external healthcare stakeholders interested in the uptake of SPHINX solution in the future.

3.3 Policy recommendations and best practices

SPHINX project sought to positively influence policy-making sector towards fostering a more well-rounded cybersecurity framework in healthcare via research-backed recommendations and best practices. To do so, the project put effort in synergizing with sister EU funder projects. Having established a network of Research and Innovation Horizon 2020 projects with shared vision to enhance the integrity and resilience of health delivery organisations, SPHINX carried out multiple joint dissemination activities targeting European Commission's representatives, including workshops and newsletters showcasing the sister projects' outputs. Detailed information regarding these activities is presented in the *D8.5 - Exploitation activities* (M36) and in *D8.8 - Dissemination activities v3* (due in March 2022).

In this context, SPHINX co-hosted a webinar with CUREX and PANACEA as the 3 projects were approaching the end of their lifecycle. The event was called '[HSE cyber-attack: a wake-up call for hospitals right across Europe](#)', its scope addressed the ransomware attack on the Irish national health service in May 2021 and elaborated on how CUREX, PANACEA and SPHINX solutions could be used not only to avoid similar attacks but also mitigate their impacts. The event, that featured also keynote speeches from representatives of DG CONNECT, ENISA, as well as the Health Executive Service of Ireland, reached a total of more than 200 participants from healthcare, cybersecurity agencies, government, academia and research domains. The webinar brought into spotlight lessons learnt by the impactful cyberattack in the Irish health sector, as well as the projects' consensus that more dedicated training, structural changes and investment are necessary to cover Healthcare's cybersecurity holistically and effectively.

In the aftermath of this event, the three projects have agreed to another synergy webinar, which is being prepared concurrently with this deliverable. This 2nd synergy event is going to focus on cyber fortification in healthcare against hybrid threats and aims to elaborate on how Europe's critical healthcare infrastructure can be prepared to avoid and mitigate malicious acts of known origin that seek for disruption instead of blackmail.

The event is directed towards policy makers of EU, top management of health delivery organisations and ICT systems and services providers. At this point, it is significant to note that the event is co-organised by SPHIX, CUREX and PANACEA under the support of Horizon Results Booster platform and that a joint recommendations document is going to be drafted presenting key takeaways from the pair of webinars, as part of the provided services of the platform.

Moreover, SPHIX end-users and technical partners in collaboration with the academic partners that developed phishing simulation tools within the H2020 EnergyShield project (<https://energy-shield.eu/>) conducted awareness campaigns to build proper cybersecurity culture in the SPHIX pilot healthcare organisations. The findings of this synergy were communicated to the institutions, and certain courses of proactive and reactive cybersecurity measures and upgrades have been triggered and implemented during the COVID-19 crisis while also establishing a proper in-house awareness campaign process about anti-phishing or anti-social engineering.

3.4 Scientific and technical knowledge

The scientific impact of SPHIX, addressed in *D1.2 - Scientific and Innovation roadmap* along with the community being built around it through the project's dissemination activities, focused on knowledge diffusion and promotion of good practice messages about technological issues in cybersecurity areas towards key target audiences, including -among others- research community and healthcare sector (hospitals, medical equipment suppliers, etc.). Being a Research and Innovation Action, SPHIX produced scientific publications to impactful journals and presentations to renowned conferences. The complete list of SPHIX scientific publications is featured in project's website, and it is presented below:

<i>Title of publication</i> <small>(conference papers, peer-reviewed articles, book chapters, etc.)</small>	<i>Date of publication</i>	<i>Authors</i>	<i>Journal Publishing House</i>	<i>Status</i>	<i>Open Access</i>		
Security Assessment as a Service Cross-Layered System for the Adoption of Digital, Personalised and Trusted Healthcare	22 Jul 2019	Evangelos K. Markakis; Yannis Nikoloudakis; Evangelos Pallis; Marco Manso	IEEE	Published	Yes		
Blockchain-Based Threat Registry Platform	19 Dec 2019	Santiago de Diego; Carlos Gonçalves; Oscar Lage; Jason Mansell; Michael Kontoulis; Serafeim Moustakidis; Barbara Guerra; Angelos Liapis	IEEE	Published	Yes		
A Survey on the Internet of Things (IoT) Forensics: Challenges, Approaches, and Open Issues	06 Jan 2020	Maria Stoyanova; Yannis Nikoloudakis; Spyridon Panagiotakis; Evangelos Pallis; Evangelos K. Markakis	IEEE	Published	Yes		
Innovative Toolkit to Assess and Mitigate Cyber Threats in the Healthcare Sector (Book Chapter)	17 Sep 2020	Marco Manso; Barbara Guerra; George Doukas; Vicky Moutmtzi	now publishers Inc. Boston - Delft	Published	Yes		
A novel feature extraction methodology using Siamese convolutional neural networks for intrusion detection	14 Aug 2020	Serafeim Moustakidis; Patrik Karlsson	Cybersecurity Springer	Published	Yes		

Sandboxing the Cyberspace for Cybersecurity Education and Learning	24 Dec 2020	Stylianos Karagiannis; Emmanouil Magkos; Christoforos; Ntantogian; Luís L. Ribeiro	Springer	Published	Yes
Reference Architectures, Platforms, and Pilots for European Smart and Healthy Living—Analysis and Comparison	6 Jul 2021	Andrej Grguric; Omar Khan; Ana Ortega-Gil; Evangelos K. Markakis; Konstantin Pozdniakov; Christos Kloukinas; Alejandro M. Medrano-Gil; Eugenio Gaeta; Giuseppe Fico; Konstantina Koloutsou	Electronics	Published	Yes
The regulatory framework for the protection of critical infrastructures against cyberthreats: Identifying shortcomings and addressing future challenges: The case of the health sector in particular	July 2021	Dimitra Markopoulou; Vagelis Papakonstantinou	Elsevier	Published	Yes
Automated and On-Demand Cybersecurity Certification	6 Sep 2021	Stylianos Karagiannis; Marco Manso; Emmanouil Magkos; Luís L. Ribeiro; Luís Campos	IEEE	Published	Yes
Act Proactively: An Intrusion Prediction Approach for Cyber Security	6 Sep 2021	Panagiotis Panagiotidis; Christos Angelidis; Ioannis Karalis; George Spyropoulos; Angelos Liapis	IEEE	Published	Yes
Consolidated Proceedings of the first ECSCI Workshop on Critical Infrastructure Protection (e-book)	26 Sep 2021	Habtamu Abie, Davide Ferrario, Ernesto Troiano, John Soldatos, Fabrizio Di Peppo, Aleksandar Jovanovic, Ilias Gkotsis, Evangelos Markakis (Eds.)	Steinbeis-Edition	Published	Yes
An Intuitive Distributed Cyber Situational Awareness Framework Within a Healthcare Environment (book chapter)	15 Sep 2021	George Doukas; Michael Kontoulis; Sotiris Pelekis; Christos Ntanos; Dimitris Askounis; Yannis Nikoloudakis; Ioannis Kefaloukos; Evangelos Pallis; Evangelos K. Markakis	now publishers Inc. Boston - Delft	Published	Yes
Hospitals' Cybersecurity Culture during the COVID-19 Crisis	7 Oct 2021	Anna Georgiadou; Ariadni Michalitsi-Psarrour; Fotios Gioulekas; Evangelos Stamatiadis; Athanasios Tzikas; Konstantinos Gounaris; Georgios Doukas; Christos Ntanos; Luís Landeiro Ribeiro; Dimitris Askounis	Healthcare	Published	Yes

A-DEMO: ATT&CK Documentation, Emulation and Mitigation Operations: Deploying and Documenting Realistic Cyberattack Scenarios - A Rootkit Case Study	Nov 2021	Stylianos Karagiannis; Alexandros Tokatlis; Sotiris Pelekis; Michael Kontoulis; George Doukas; Christos Ntanos; Emmanouil Magkos	PCI 2021: 25th Pan-Hellenic Conference on Informatics	Published	Yes
A Cybersecurity Culture Survey Targeting Healthcare Critical Infrastructures	Jan 2022	Fotios Gioulekas; Evangelos Stamatiadis; Athanasios Tzikas; Konstantinos Gounaris; Anna Georgiadou; Ariadni Michalitsi-Psarrou; Georgios Doukas; Michael Kontoulis; Yannis Nikoloudakis; Sergiu Marin; Ricardo Cabecinha; Christos Ntanos	Healthcare	Published	Yes

Table 3 Complete list of SPHINX scientific publications

In addition to the scientific publications, the cyber security techniques, tools and methodologies stemmed from SPHINX enhanced the educational modules of the academic project partners. In this respect, NTUA has enriched PhD courses through the extensive research conducted during SPHINX that included attack simulation, user behaviour analysis simulation, cyber risk modelling, network analysis, while it envisions to incorporate the acquired knowledge in educational modules. Moreover, HMU plans to release its component as open-source software to facilitate university's courses on cybersecurity. Further information about SPHINX consortium exploitation plans is provided in the analysis of partners' exploitation survey (Chapter 4).

In general, it should be mentioned that for further information about the exploitation activities performed by SPHINX partners a detailed list is provided by the *D8.5 - Exploitation activities* (M36). The deliverable presents the efforts of SPHINX partners to promote key exploitable project's results towards key target audiences and ensure their sustainability following the project's end.

4 Consortium's Exploitation and Sustainability Options

During the last year of the project, a 2-round survey (Appendix I, Appendix II) was conducted among the consortium to collect information concerning all partners' strategy to exploit and sustain the SPHINX project outcomes both at individual level and at the level of the consortium as a whole. The survey prompted partners to analyse ideas and opinions about the exploitation prospects of the project and the SPHINX Toolkit components that have been developed. Overall key findings are presented as follows:

4.1.1 Benefits from SPHINX project, joint exploitation initiative, key steps to be taken and obstacles to be addressed

At first, partners elaborated on the **benefits attained from participating in SPHINX project**. There was a consensus among the consortium on how the project helped every partner to gain knowledge in specific cybersecurity domains, such as network monitoring, data management, risk assessment and threat intelligence.

Through the acquired knowledge, partners stated that they have deepened their skills in terms of developing and deploying their technologies. As a result, partners argued that they have managed to enhance their portfolio of expertise. A broader understanding of cybersecurity -especially in health sector- was reached and partners supported that the identified lessons and best practices from SPHINX have built a solid background for their further research.

Partners, also, commented that strong collaboration ties have grown throughout the project implementation, since joint efforts were necessary in many cases.

In terms of **what SPHINX outcomes, they plan to exploit**, partners focused in two main points. At the one side, partners (mainly non-profit, but not explicitly) indicated that they will leverage the scientific knowledge produced within the project to draft scientific publications, enhance academic modules and apply it to future research projects. At the other side, for-profit partners, primarily, emphasized in further developing the components created within the project, so that they could eventually prepare for market launch, either as integrated in their own portfolios or as part of a joint exploitation.

Regarding a **joint exploitation of SPHINX**, all partners (non-profit and for-profit alike) expressed their willingness to participate in a joint initiative dedicated to further sustain and exploit SPHINX beyond the project. The shared interest comprised both commercial endeavours and further deployment of SPHIX in future actions and projects.

A common point raised among partners was the analysis and specification of the conditions of further exploitation of SPHINX before any initiative is set in place.

What is more, partners brought multiple points forward on what **key actions are necessary for a successfully sustaining and exploiting SPHINX** results once the project is completed, especially the SPHINX Toolkit. Partners stressed that such an endeavour would need substantial founding (e.g., future EU funding, external founding from business angles and/or start-up accelerators). In addition, a clear and well-defined value proposition of SPHINX Toolkit backed by thorough market analyses is necessary according to partners. Moreover, it was prominent in partners' answers that effective promotion of SPHINX Toolkit including demos and pitching presentations is required.

Furthermore, partners stated that SPHINX Toolkit components should be further developed and tested in real-life conditions in order to enhance their function, interoperability and user friendliness. Aligned with the future work on development and deployment, partners argued that components should be introduced to each corresponding partner services portfolio and that clear Intellectual Property Rights should be established before any launch of joint exploitation initiative.

When it comes to what that can **hinder a successful exploitation of SPHINX**, partners recognised a few main obstacles that revolve around SPHINX Toolkit TRL and the differences among its components, the customers' interest and the market share.

In more detail, it was noted the joint SPHINX initiative should mitigate the risk of lack of coordinated maintenance of SPHINX, which also entails the development needs that vary due to different TRL status among components. In addition, the heterogeneity of goals between partners was highlighted as issue to be addressed in order to ensure fruitful collaboration of the joint initiative.

Finally, partners mentioned that the healthcare sector documents low cybersecurity awareness which may limit the interest of potential customers. Also, the large market share occupied by big tech companies constitutes an obstacle, according to partners' answers, towards building trust in a alternative solution provided by a consortium of partners, like SPHINX.

4.1.2 SPHINX Toolkit components exploitation insights

In addition to the above-mentioned overall answers about SPHINX exploitation and sustainability, the survey aimed to collect insights regarding SPHINX Toolkit components. The information below was provided by each partner in sub-fields of the survey in order to draft a more specific outline of exploitation and sustainability options per component.

It should be noted that, among other input, the survey collected answers regarding the potential pricing of the SPHINX components once they reach a commercially exploitable status. This information was taken into account for the overall estimation of SPHINX's business plan; however, it is not going to be disclosed in this public deliverable.

NTUA

Realtime Cyber Risk Assessment (RCRA)	
Potential customers	Security Analysts, Researchers
Competitors offering similar solutions?	No
Brief value proposition	The component is opensource and it is not domain specific. It can capture better user's perspective.
TRL by the end of the project	TRL 5
Estimated development needed to reach TRL 7	Approximately 40 PMs
Commercial services planned?	No

Potential customers	Security Analysts, Researchers
Competitors offering similar solutions?	No

Brief value proposition	The component is opensource and it is not domain specific. T provides an easy way to retain information from different sources in a unified manner, to support incident investigation efforts
TRL by the end of the project	TRL 3
Estimated development needed to reach TRL 7	Approximately 60 PMs
Commercial services planned?	No

Potential customers	Security Analysts, Researchers
Competitors offering similar solutions?	No
Brief value proposition	The component is opensource and it is not domain specific. It can capture better user's perspective.
TRL by the end of the project	TRL 5
Estimated development needed to reach TRL 7	Approximately 40 PMs
Commercial services planned?	No

Potential customers	Security Analysts, Researchers
Competitors offering similar solutions?	https://github.com/markusring/CIDDS
Brief value proposition	The component Includes implementations personalised to the healthcare domain and implements a variety of healthcare related user profiles
TRL by the end of the project	TRL 3
Estimated development needed to reach TRL 7	72 PMs
Commercial services planned?	No

FINT

Potential customers	Hospitals, Medical centres, SMEs, Cybersecurity Awareness and Training professionals, Cybersecurity Research institutes
Competitors offering similar solutions?	There are several commercial and open-source alternatives (e.g. Blumira virtual honeypots , OWASP honeypot.) https://github.com/markusring/CIDDS
Brief value proposition	The component provides a solution that can be both accommodated in cloud and on premise (addressing as such any Cloud-derived security/privacy concerns) deployments providing a consistent experience form the users; further to that the utilisation of acceleration from the hardware versions enables for the edge based cyber-attack detection and analysis by providing results on the spot; finally the, offer of an open API and the adoption of standards (e.g. STIX) for sharing the cyber-attacks information promotes the solution's inter-operability by a) facilitating its integration in already deployed cyber-attack detection warning ecosystems and b) by enabling it to exploit third party AI algorithms towards extending the detection capabilities range. In this context, the honeypots will contribute to detecting faster the launched cyber-attacks, thus enabling the business to take faster the proper actions and as such minimise the negative impact on the business in terms of affected assets (e.g., disrupted IT systems and services), lost profits from the services' disruption, lost reputation, and lost work hours.
TRL by the end of the project	TRL 4
Estimated development needed to reach TRL 7	24 PMs
Commercial services planned?	The HW and SW HP flavours tailored for being deployed either at the edge (premises of the customers) or in centralised cloud-based deployments. A community edition will also be supported.

Potential customers	Hospitals, Medical centres, SMEs, Cybersecurity Awareness and Training professionals, CSIRT teams, Cybersecurity Research institutes
Competitors offering similar solutions?	There are several commercial and open-source alternatives (e.g. LookingGlass , Anomali ThreatStream , IBM X-Force Exchange) https://github.com/markusring/CIDDS
Brief value proposition	The component provides a solution that can be both accommodated in cloud and on premise (addressing as such any Cloud-derived security/privacy concerns) deployments providing a consistent experience to the users; further to that the envisaged automated integration of tailored to the specific application domain needs and particularities cyber-threat intelligence information from various external

	repositories, the seamless encapsulation/adaptation of the information in a common standardised language (i.e. STIX) and the sharing of actionable cyber intelligence information via open APIs promotes the solution's inter-operability with other cyber-security actuators towards forming a collaborative threat analysis, automated threat exchange and automated detection and response ecosystem enabling for faster detection and response times when dealing with cybersecurity incidents thus minimising their negative impact on the business in terms of affected assets (e.g. disrupted IT systems and services), lost profits from the services' disruption, lost reputation, and lost work hours.
TRL by the end of the project	TRL 4
Estimated development needed to reach TRL 7	24 PMs
Commercial services planned?	A community edition free of charge for the publicly shareable Threat intelligence information will be available. A commercial service will be available for the actionable tailored to the needs and requirements of the requesting entity's specific application domain.

KT

Analytics Engine (AE)	
Potential customers	Public or Private Institutions, Research and Innovation Partnerships
Competitors offering similar solutions?	Yes
Brief value proposition	The main advantages of the AE solution are to support the user in decision-making with the provision of multiple visualizations such as pie/line charts and bar plots and also descriptive statistics of aggregate information.
TRL by the end of the project	TRL 5
Estimated development needed to reach TRL 7	12-14 PMs
Commercial services planned?	Yes. After the end of the project, we will do a market Analysis in order to find potential customers and we will develop the AE further based on their needs to create a more competitive commercial product.

Analytics Engine (AE)	
Potential customers	Public or Private Institutions, Research and Innovation Partnerships

Competitors offering similar solutions?	Yes
Brief value proposition	The main advantages of the DSS solution are the early detection of the categories of cyber-attacks Denial of Service (DoS), and Probe with Machine Learning techniques and the targeted response plan after a cyber-attack occurs with a confidence level of the effectiveness of the response plan.
TRL by the end of the project	TRL 5
Estimated development needed to reach TRL 7	20-24 PMs
Commercial services planned?	Yes. After the end of the project, we will do a market Analysis in order to find potential customers and we will develop the DSS further based on their needs to create a more competitive commercial product.

SIMAVI

Interactive Dashboards (ID)	
Potential customers	Small and medium companies, state-owned companies in the health domain
Competitors offering similar solutions?	IBM Cloud Pak for Security
Brief value proposition	The advantages provided by the ID are the user-friendliness of the application and its flexibility- it allows customization per any clients wishes or needs. Another advantage would be that the ID provides a custom-built plugin for displaying alerts integrated with suggestions from DSS for the users and that it can be expanded for further visualisations and plugins.
TRL by the end of the project	TRL 5
Estimated development needed to reach TRL 7	18 PMs
Commercial services planned?	Service-licenced for a stand-alone solution or integration into cybersecurity applications

Potential customers	Small and medium companies, state-owned companies in the health domain
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Competitors offering similar solutions?	Cisco SecureX Platform; Trend Micro Vision One; Medigate Device Security Platform (MDSP); IBM Cloud Pak for Security; IBM Security Qradar
Brief value proposition	DTM manages to combine technologies such as T-shark, Logstash and Suricata. It can send a lot of data in real-time, being very detailed in terms of network traffic information. It can also extend its functionalities, being able to present GeoIP information, the reputation of the Ips, vulnerabilities and the addition of custom rules for the detection of irregularities in the network.
TRL by the end of the project	TRL 5
Estimated development needed to reach TRL 7	24 PMs
Commercial services planned?	Service-licenced for a stand-alone solution or integration into cybersecurity applications

Anomaly Detection (AD)	
Potential customers	Small and medium companies, state-owned companies in the health domain
Competitors offering similar solutions?	Cisco SecureX Platform; Medigate Device Security Platform (MDSP); IBM Cloud Pak for Security
Brief value proposition	Anomaly detection allows the configuration of existing algorithms through interactive methods for users, analyzing and transmitting a lot of data in real-time.
TRL by the end of the project	TRL 5
Estimated development needed to reach TRL 7	30 PMs
Commercial services planned?	Service-licenced for a stand-alone solution or integration into cybersecurity applications

AiDEAS

AiDEAS	
Potential customers	Any organisation that uses a Honey Pot as part of their cybersecurity infrastructure.
Competitors offering similar solutions?	Not at the moment

Brief value proposition	Most of the reported scientific research has been devoted on building complex ML/DL architectures adopting a brute force approach towards the maximization of their detection capacity. To enhance user's trust and understanding on data without sacrificing on accuracy, the SPHINX MLID component contributes to the transformation of the available data collected by the HP into a single actionable and easy-to-understand risk indicator.
TRL by the end of the project	TRL 5
Estimated development needed to reach TRL 7	12 PMs
Commercial services planned?	Jointly with the SPHINX partners and FINT

HMU

Potential customers	The component can be widely used in universities and academic courses on cybersecurity
Competitors offering similar solutions?	N/A
Brief value proposition	The component is opensource and can be utilised and "tweaked" to match each user's needs
TRL by the end of the project	TRL 5
Estimated development needed to reach TRL 7	40 PMs
Commercial services planned?	No

PDMFC

Potential customers	Mainly medium and big European companies
Competitors offering similar solutions?	Yes
Brief value proposition	Different from most competitors that are commercializing a prior generation SIEM, SPHINX aims to build and commercialize a next-gen SIEM with low budget, low resources requirements, fast performance, low maintenance, Mitre ATT&CK aligned, powerful correlation engine, fast source customisation, quick deployment and cloud-ready. The most

	relevant component of each SIEM is how whether or not they age well, or dwell into a mess. With SPHINX SIEM we align with open-source best practices and align our detection engine with the threat intelligence provided and maintained by the open-source community. Specifically, we are talking about SIGMA and YARA rules, synchronized with ATT&CK framework, with custom respond and recovery extensions.
TRL by the end of the project	TRL 5/6
Estimated development needed to reach TRL 7	3 PMs
Commercial services planned?	Yes, PDMFC plans to go to market with a complete SIEM solution

EDGE

Potential customers	Healthcare authorities (agencies within the healthcare ecosystem with a complex ICT infrastructure and having the responsibility of managing health-related data); Healthcare service providers (hospitals, clinics, private practices)
Competitors offering similar solutions?	No
Brief value proposition	The unique proposition value of the SPHINX Third-Party API is the capability to enable a user to validate or certify third-party components as secure and SPHINX-compliant, before including them in their ICT infrastructure and networks. If the components are not assessed as secure (in the SPHINX compliance scale), the user becomes aware of its identified vulnerabilities and of the proposed measures to attain the SPHINX-compliant status.
TRL by the end of the project	TRL 5/6
Estimated development needed to reach TRL 7	6 PMs
Commercial services planned?	Yes – jointly with the SPHINX partners (for this component only applies if the SPHiNX System is in place).

TEC

Potential customers	The tool is key for many verticals such as transport, education, smart buildings and etc.

Competitors offering similar solutions?	Similar solutions are built by competitors such as IBM but they are expensive to implement.
Brief value proposition	The tool does not just encrypt information, it also provides data anonymization and privacy capabilities.
TRL by the end of the project	TRL 5/6
Estimated development needed to reach TRL 7	7 PMs
Commercial services planned?	Yes – jointly with the SPHINX partners (for this component only applies if the SPHINX System is in place).

TECNALIA

Potential customers	Medical providers and auditors, but the tool is easily adapted to fit any organization needs.
Competitors offering similar solutions?	No
Brief value proposition	BBTR offers an anti-tampering registry that acts as a preventive security measure by notifying third parties when they are about to suffer a security incident. It also can be useful for auditors, who can query the registry and see the timeline of the different incidents with the guarantee that they have not been tampered
TRL by the end of the project	TRL 5
Estimated development needed to reach TRL 7	20 PMs
Commercial services planned?	TECNALIA will find a partner/cybersecurity company that will be willing to incorporate the BBTR as part of their portfolio. TECNALIA will collaborate in the maintenance and evolution of the BBTR as well as training the organisation in the delivery of the service.

ICOM

Potential customers	The Service Manager role is to facilitate integration in total IT solutions of various building blocks implemented by various third parties. As such, the Service Manager is not a direct offering to potential customers (i.e., a software product that they can buy), but a facilitator for the integration
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	of a total IT solution for which the customers would pay as an integrated product.
Competitors offering similar solutions?	IT Integration services are offered by many different stakeholders in regional and global level.
Brief value proposition	The Service Manager comprises an in-house implemented component for facilitating integration among third party tools. As such it relieves ICOM from using (and paying license for) third party tools that would play this role and therefore can lower the overall cost of the total solution and make us more competitive in tenders.
TRL by the end of the project	TRL 5
Estimated development needed to reach TRL 7	7 PMs
Commercial services planned?	One of the Business Units of ICOM focuses on ICT services and Solutions. This BU offers commercial services of turnkey IT solutions integration, deployment and maintenance / operation. The R&D group (belonging to another BU of the company) is in discussions with the former BU as for the formulation of a strategy for exploitation of the Service Manager in future commercial projects where applicable.

5 SPHINX Business Model

The SPHINX business model was developed to guide the commercialisation potential of the SPHINX Toolkit. The Business Model presented in this section integrates insights which were acquired through work that took place between all members of the consortium. Two exploitation workshops took place during the last year of the project (online in February 2021 and face to face in October 2021). During these workshops the exploitation potential of the SPHINX Toolkit was discussed, and a preliminary business model was developed and presented below.

The Business Model Canvas¹ methodology was used (**Error! Reference source not found.**). Business Model Canvas allows to describe, design, visualise, challenge, invent and pivot business models. The Business Model Canvas was selected because:

- it has a widespread acceptance among business and academics,
- it is simple and easy to understand,
- it is effective and efficient at communicating and documenting business models,
- it has been used by a number of practitioners in different industries and areas,
- it can be updated easily, and
- it is easy to adopt.

Figure 3: Business Model Canvas

The business model presented here can be used by any entity that is already established or will be established in the future as a start-up (e.g., a SPHINX company). That means that the business model considers the further development needed for all the components (for the SPHINX Toolkit to reach a mature state – TRL-7) and the IPRs related to the acquisition of rights for use of the different components that have been developed by all technical partners.

¹ <https://strategyzer.com/canvas>

Figure 4: SPHINX Toolkit Business Model Canvas

A block-by-block description of the business model of the SPHINX Toolkit follows:

5.1 Customer segments

The customer segments building block presents the potential customers of the SPHINX Toolkit. In other words, the target audience to whom SPHINX Toolkit intends to offer its value proposition. Successful business models go beyond what customers want, towards understanding the tasks customers are trying to accomplish and problems they encounter related to them. This exercise has already been implemented in the early phases of SPHINX project and as an outcome, the SPHINX components have been developed taking into account the needs of **Healthcare institutions**. So, based on a) the initial scope of the SPHINX project, b) the research that was conducted during the preparation of “D8.9 Market Analysis” and c) bilateral discussions between partners of the consortium and potential end users, we have identified **Healthcare institutions** as the core customers that would be willing to pay for SPHINX Toolkit. Based on their size and cybersecurity needs, we can segment the Healthcare institutions market into the following categories:

- Small healthcare organisations (e.g., clinics, rehabilitation centres)
- Hospitals and primary healthcare centres
- Clusters of healthcare provision

5.2 Value proposition

The value proposition describes the bundle of SPHINX products and services that create value to the customers described in the previous section (Healthcare institutions). SPHINX Toolkit provides an embedded, smart and

robust security awareness layer, able to identify modern and advance cyber threats, enhanced with a personalised data security management tool. Some of the most important state-of-the-art services that SPHINX Toolkit offers are:

- Vulnerability Management
- Traffic Monitoring
- Forensics
- Network Intrusion and Detection System
- Risk Management
- Asset Management
- Log Management
- Threat Intelligence
- Encryption
- Privacy
- Decision Support
- Analytics
- Automation

At the same time SPHINX Toolkit:

- **handles the data of a large number of devices and services**, covering a wide range of use case scenarios; and
- offers users/admins the possibility to stay informed at any time via **highly comprehensive visual analytics**.

The value of SPHINX lies in the combination of the use of these different services within a Healthcare environment. The fact that the SPHINX components have been designed and developed specifically for Healthcare institutions is of paramount importance for the value of SPHINX Toolkit.

5.3 Channels

Channels are used to get the product/service from the firm to the customer. There are five channel phases throughout the sales process, namely: awareness, evaluation, purchase, delivery and after sales. SPHINX has a precise action plan on how to cope with the each one of them.

- ✓ **Awareness:** The first phase consists of actions which will enhance the awareness of SPHINX Toolkit among its potential customers. In order to introduce its service, SPHINX will: establish its own website, make use of social media and networks, participate in relevant scientific conferences and organise workshops. Additionally, SPHINX will establish partnerships with the European Union Agency for Cybersecurity (ENISA), European Commission marketplaces (i.e., Cyberwatching.eu Marketplace) and web-portals of Health Authorities all of which are considered to be in direct contact with potential customers.
- ✓ **Evaluation:** After becoming aware of the SPHINX Toolkit, potential customers will need to execute some kind of evaluation of the services offered. SPHINX will have an online demo which potential customers can try and get a hands-on experience of the Toolkit. Next to that, a video and a manual will demonstrate the use of the Toolkit and its capabilities.
- ✓ **Purchase & Delivery:** After evaluating the service, potential customers that want to use the SPHINX Toolkit will have the opportunity to select their preferred service both through the SPHINX website or by contacting a SPHINX representative (online and offline). The delivery of the services acquired will be offered on demand. That means that a customer will express an interest and the SPHINX developers will install the requested services at the customer premises.
- ✓ **After sales:** Customers will be able to contact the customer service department via e-mail and phone. On site visit to the customer is also possible.

5.4 Customer relationships

Customer relationships are the links a company establishes between itself and its different customer segments. They describe the types of relationships that the company has with the specific customer segments. SPHINX targets large institutions and organizations instead of individuals. Consequently, holding customers is less

expensive than acquiring new ones. Therefore, SPHINX focuses from its very beginning on a customer retention policy. In accordance with the retention policy, SPHINX will set up the following types of customer relationships:

- ✓ **Co-creation:** SPHINX aims to co-create value with its customers, for its customers. The customer service department is going to be in charge for collecting feedback from customers for ideas on new features development and bug fixing.
- ✓ **Community building:** SPHINX will also build and maintain an online community to exchange knowledge, solve problems and improve the value of the services offered. Community building can also assist in better understanding customers and further develop the Toolkit according to their needs.

5.5 Revenue streams

Revenue streams are the methods that a company uses to collect money from its customers. In essence, it is a way of earning money and a way to protect it. There are several revenue models that already exist:

- ✓ Commerce (retailing, marketplace, aggregator, group buying, downloads, auction etc),
- ✓ Subscription (Software as a Service, Service as a Service, Content as a Service, Freemium SAAS, Donations, Support and maintenance etc),
- ✓ Licensing (per application, per site, patent licensing etc),
- ✓ Data (user data, business data, user intelligence, search data).

SPHINX will use the **Licensing** as the core revenue stream to offer SPHINX Toolkit in three different versions:

Basic service (targeted to small healthcare institutions such as clinics). The Basic service includes installation and permission to use of the following (6) components:

- **Service Manager** (for automation)
- **Common Integration Platform** (for automation)
- **Interactive Dashboards** (for UX/UI, analytics, notifications)
- **Security Information and Event Management** (for log management, threat intelligence, forensics)
- **Data Traffic Monitoring** (for traffic monitoring, forensics, network intrusion detection)
- **Vulnerability Assessment as a Service** (for vulnerability management)

Pro service (targeted to hospitals and healthcare centres). The Pro service includes installation and permission to use all the components of the Basic service (6) plus installation and permission to use the following components (7):

- **Real-time Cyber Risk Assessment** (for risk management and asset management)
- **Artificial Intelligence (AI) Honeypot (HP)** (for threat intelligence and forensics)
- **Machine Learning-empowered Intrusion Detection** (for intrusion detection)
- **Forensic Data Collection Engine** (for forensics)
- **Anonymisation and Privacy** (for encryption and privacy)
- **Analytic Engine** (for Analytics)
- **Knowledge Base** (for threat intelligence)

Max service (targeted to large clusters). The Max services includes installation and permission to use all the components of the Pro service (13) plus installation and permission to use the following components (7):

- **Anomaly Detection** (for threat detection)
- **Homomorphic Encryption** (for encryption and privacy)
- **Decision Support System** (for decision support)
- **Sandbox** (for threat detection)
- **Blockchain Based Threats Registry** (for threat intelligence)
- **SPHINX Application Programming Interface for Third Parties** (for automation)
- **Common Cybersecurity Toolbox** (for automation)

Customers are also able to ask for yearly **Maintenance and Support** for their preferred services. This includes support for bug fixing, support for software updates etc.

SPHINX will also offer tailored **Training sessions** to interested customers.

5.6 Key resources

Key resources are the most important assets to make the business model happen. Without them the company cannot create and deliver the value proposition. SPHINX, will need the following key resources:

- ✓ **Physical:** SPHINX will need company facilities in which most tasks will be executed.
- ✓ **Finance-Funds:** SPHINX will need financing either through a business loan or a fund or combination of the two.
- ✓ **Intellectual resources:** before start operating, the SPHINX entity should **register a trade mark**. When operating the different services, **Intellectual Property Rights** for the components should be considered. The SPHINX entity should establish agreements with all technical partners that have developed the different SPHINX components.
- ✓ **Personnel:** the company will need developers, testers, customer service, sales force, a manager, a product manager and a system administrator. As in most start-ups, the organisational structure is going to be quite flexible. The plan for the personnel includes four people performing several roles. One person will execute the tasks assigned to the manager, the salesperson. Two will take over the tasks associated to the developer, tester and systems administrator and the last one will be dedicated to customer service. It is obvious that since different components are involved, the SPHINX entity will establish synergies with the companies that have developed the different components in order to enhance the TRL of the different components.

5.7 Key activities

The Key Activities building block describes the most important things a company must do to make its business model work. In SPHINX the most important activities that the potential company should do are the following:

- ✓ **Software Development:** Since most of the SPHINX components have TRL 5, further development is needed in order to reach the expected TRL 7. Some components are open source, so the development could be implemented by the SPHINX entity. For the others, synergies and agreements with the companies that have developed the different components are needed.
- ✓ **Maintenance:** The maintenance of the SPHINX Toolkit includes bug fixing. These bugs are reported by customers and communicated to the developers through the customer service department.
- ✓ **New Features Development:** Developing, testing and launching new features are tasks assigned to the developer and tester. They are responsible of bringing in life new features inspired by customers and communicated to them through the customer service department.
- ✓ **Sales process:** The sales process includes tasks performed by the salesperson such as management of the website, handling of social media and network, participation in conferences, organizing workshops, creating videos and online demos.

- ✓ **Customer Service:** Supporting customers through e-mail and phone. Forward bug reports and ideas for new features development to developers.

5.8 Key partners

The Key Partners building block describes the network of suppliers and partners that make the business model work. Key partners for running the SPHINX business model should be:

- ✓ **SPHINX technical partners:** As already stated, the SPHINX entity should establish synergies and agreements with all SPHINX technical partners in order to provide support to the components they have developed.
- ✓ **Healthcare associations:** Partnerships can be established with different healthcare associations at EU level.
- ✓ **Cybersecurity agencies:** Partnerships can also be established with cybersecurity agencies e.g., ENISA.
- ✓ **Financial Institutions:** This partnership could provide a business loan or liquidity.
- ✓ **Funds:** Partnership with venture capital funds that will invest in the SPHINX entity.
- ✓ **Industry:** partnerships with key Industry Stakeholders that are engaged with the Health Sector and also with manufacturers of medical devices due to the importance of security by design for the modern healthcare equipment.
- ✓ **Standardisation Authorities:** both in national and European level, such as Health Ministries and other Public Authorities that supervise Healthcare.

5.9 Cost structure

The Cost Structure describes all costs incurred to operate the business model. The cost structure is highly related to three pre-defined blocks of the business model, Key activities, Key resources and Key partners.

Fixed costs:

Fixed costs are those that exist by time the firm is launched. The fixed costs for SPHINX are:

- ✓ **Office facilities:** Office facilities costs include the monthly total cost of using an office and every cost associated to it such as power supply, consumables etc.
- ✓ **Hardware for developing & testing:** These are servers which are essential for developing new features, fixing bugs and testing the new releases before adapting them.

Variable costs:

Variable costs change proportionally to the activity of a business. SPHINX considers the following variable costs:

- ✓ **Staff:** SPHINX will need at least two developers to operate in its very beginning, one product manager and one customer support officer. The average salary is subject to the country where the firm will be established. The recruiting policy will depend on the customer volume and the needs associated to them.
- ✓ **Synergies with technical partners (IPRs):** Further development of the different components is needed. Agreements with technical partners will be established and this includes also costs for these agreements.
- ✓ **Marketing and sales:** Costs for expenditures related to marketing and sales are also foreseen. This includes also costs for participation in events, organisation of workshops, development of promotional materials (both online and tangible) etc.

6 SPHINX Business plan

6.1 Background

SPHINX is a Research and Innovation action that delivers the SPHINX Toolkit composed of 20 stand-alone components that have been developed by eleven different technical partners. The consortium has already implemented actions to enhance the exploitation and sustainability potential of the different components and of the knowledge that was generated during their development. Some components will be commercially exploited by the IPR holders, some components will be available as open source and all components have already enhanced the technical know-how of the beneficiaries which intend to use this knowledge to make business and/or to enhance their research capacity.

With regards to the business potential of the SPHINX Toolkit and since this is a research project it is obvious that further development is needed for the SPHINX Toolkit to reach a mature state. In that respect, the first exercise that the consortium implemented was to check the current TRL of the components and to estimate the PMs needed for each component to reach a TRL-7 (Table 3).

SPHINX component	Responsible	TRL now	PMs to reach		
1	Service Manager	ICOM	5	7	
2	Common Integration Platform*	ICOM	service N/A	0	
3	Interactive Dashboards (ID)	SIMAVI	5	18	
4	Data Traffic Monitoring (DTM)	SIMAVI	5	24	
5	Vulnerability Assessment as a Service (VAaaS)	HMU	5	40	
6	Security Information and Event Management (SIEM)	PDMFC	5	3	
7	Real-time Cyber Risk Assessment (RCRA)	NTUA	5	40	
8	Artificial Intelligence (AI) Honeypot (HP)	FINT	4	24	
9	Machine Learning-empowered Intrusion Detection (MLID)	AiDEAS	5	12	
10	Forensic Data Collection Engine (FDCE)	NTUA	3	60	
11	Anonymisation and Privacy (AP)	PDMFC	5	10	
12	Analytic Engine (AE)	KT	5	12	
13	Knowledge Base (KB)	FINT	4	24	
14	Anomaly Detection (AD)	SIMAVI	5	30	
15	Homomorphic Encryption (HE)	Tech Inspire	5	7	
16	Decision Support System (DSS)	KT	5	24	

17	Sandbox (SB)	PDMFC	4	24
18	Blockchain Based Threats Registry (BBTR)	TECHNALIA	5	20
19	SPHINX Application Programming Interface for Third Parties (S-API)	EDGE	5-6	6
20	Common Cybersecurity Toolbox	HMU	4	24

Table 4: TRL of SPHINX components and estimated effort to reach TRL-7

For the **Basic service** that is composed of the first six components of Table 3, the consortium estimates that approximately **92 PMs** of further development is needed to reach TRL-7. For the **Pro service** that is composed of the first 13 components, the consortium estimates that approximately **274 PMs** of further development is needed to reach TRL-7. For the **Max service**, **409 PMs** of further development is needed.

The second exercise that the consortium implemented is to assess the cost of the three services. Technical partners were asked to estimate how much would they charge for every component. This exercise helped us estimate the cost for each service. The cost for the **Basic service** could be **110.000€**, the cost for the **Pro service** could be **180.000€** and the cost for the **Max service** could be **280.000€**. At this point and since this deliverable is public, we would not like to disclose the prices for each component individually for two reasons. Firstly, because some partners are already developing their business models and business plans for their components, and secondly because it is an estimation, and the prices might change in the near future.

6.2 The SPHINX company

In this section we present the SPHINX business case. We propose the establishment of a company whose mission would be to offer a health tailored universal Cybersecurity Toolkit to Health Delivery Organisations in order to enhance their cyber protection and to ensure patient data privacy and integrity. Shareholders of this company could be all SPHINX partners that are interested in the commercialisation of project results.

The following services will be offered by the company:

Basic service (targeted to small healthcare institutions such as clinics). The Basic service includes installation and permission to use of the following (6) components:

- Service Manager (for automation)
- Common Integration Platform (for automation)
- Interactive Dashboards (for UX/UI, analytics, notifications)
- Security Information and Event Management (for log management, threat intelligence, forensics)
- Data Traffic Monitoring (for traffic monitoring, forensics, network intrusion detection)
- Vulnerability Assessment as a Service (for vulnerability management)

Pro service (targeted to hospitals and healthcare centres). The Pro service includes installation and permission to use all the components of the Basic service (6) plus installation and permission to use the following components (7):

- Real-time Cyber Risk Assessment (for risk management and asset management)
- Artificial Intelligence (AI) Honeypot (HP) (for threat intelligence and forensics)
- Machine Learning-empowered Intrusion Detection (for intrusion detection)
- Forensic Data Collection Engine (for forensics)
- Anonymisation and Privacy (for encryption and privacy)
- Analytic Engine (for Analytics)
- Knowledge Base (for threat intelligence)

Max service (targeted to large clusters). The Max services includes installation and permission to use all the components of the Pro service (13) plus installation and permission to use the following components (7):

- Anomaly Detection (for threat detection)
- Homomorphic Encryption (for encryption and privacy)
- Decision Support System (for decision support)
- Sandbox (for threat detection)
- Blockchain Based Threats Registry (for threat intelligence)
- SPHINX Application Programming Interface for Third Parties (for automation)
- Common Cybersecurity Toolbox (for automation)

6.3 SPHINX IPRs

According to “World Intellectual Property Organization (WIPO) (2011), Intellectual Property Rights (IPRs) are the legal rights which result from intellectual activity in the industrial, scientific, literary and artistic fields. IPRs cover two main areas:

- industrial property (inventions: patents, utility models; trademarks; industrial designs and protected designations of origin), and
- copyright (represented by literary, musical, artistic, photographic and audio-visual works).

In SPHINX, as in every other EU research project, there are two IPR issues that need to be handled. First of all, **the management of the pre-existing know-how (background IPRs)** that exist in terms of commercialisation of the final product/service/result, and secondly **how the knowledge generated within the project (foreground IPRs) should be protected** by the SPHINX consortium after the end of the project. This section provides an analysis of these issues.

Background IPRs are Intellectual Property Rights that existed before the beginning of project. It is knowledge held by participants prior to their accession to the Grand Agreement, as well as any IPRs which are needed for carrying out the project. In SPHINX, there are Background IPRs reported in the Consortium Agreement.

Foreground IPRs are usually results, materials and knowledge generated in the project. They are IPRs that are generated within the project period and owned by the participant who generated them. When foreground is generated jointly, it is jointly owned, unless participants concerned agree on a different solution. In SPHINX foreground IPRs are divided in two categories:

- The ones that were generated within the project period and belong to the SPHINX Consortium such as the project logo, the project acronym, the domain name etc.
- The ones that were generated within the project period and belong to participant(s) who generated them.

For the first category (IPRs belonging to the SPHINX Consortium) we identify the following:

- The **project logo**, the **project acronym** (SPHINX) and the **project domain name** (<https://sphinx-project.eu>) belong to the SPHINX consortium. After the end of the project, the logo, the acronym and the domain name will belong to the members of the consortium that are interested in the sustainability, exploitation and commercialisation of the project’s results.

For the second category (Foreground IPRs belonging to one or more partners), we identify the SPHINX components. The IPRs of the components belong to the technical partners that have developed them. In **Error! Reference source not found.**, the partners that own the IPRs of the SPHINX components are presented.

6.4 Vision, mission and objectives

The triplet consisted of Vision, Mission and Objectives defines much of the strategic planning of an organisation. It shows what the organisation visions as the identical future state and how it plans to move towards it. The SPHINX company has set its own Vision, Mission and Objectives which are presented subsequently.

Vision

The SPHINX company visions a world where Health Delivery Organisations and their staff are aware and well informed of the cybersecurity risks they face and have access to a transparent cybersecurity Toolkit where with minimal effort they become aware and understand the cybersecurity risks and take informed decisions affecting their cyber-physical security and privacy.

Mission

The following statement defines the company's mission:

The mission of the SPHINX company is to support Health Delivery Organisations in enhancing the cyber protection of their IT ecosystem ensuring data privacy and integrity.

Objectives

In order to accomplish its mission, the SPHINX company has to reach its objective which is:

The SPHINX company's goal is to become a financially healthy organisation which will lead the healthcare cybersecurity market by providing technologically advanced solutions, capable to be tailored to the cybersecurity needs of health delivery organisations of any size.

6.5 Operational plan

The operational plan aims to contribute to the setup of the SPHINX company. The plan consists of four stages, namely Investment and preparation stage, Foundation stage, Development Stage and Day to day operations.

6.5.1 Investment and preparation stage

Further funding is needed for the SPHINX Toolkit to reach a mature state. During this stage, the partners interested in the commercialization potential of SPHINX Toolkit are searching for funding (>1.2M) in order to support the development of the components. In parallel, agreements are established with the company owners and all the IPR holders of the SPHINX components. Once the capital investment is found, the finalisation of the development begins. This stage is estimated to last 6 to 12 months and in the financial plan, it is mentioned as Year 0.

6.5.1.1 Capitalisation sources

Self-funding

The SPHINX company can initially rely on capital from its founders in order to operate. Capital contributions among founders might vary in nature, including hard cash, infrastructure, technical know-how or personnel months.

Public funds

SPHINX company can apply for grants from the European commission through upcoming research funding programmes. Next to that, there are going to be more attempts to acquire funding from various calls and programmes, either at the EU or at the national level.

SPHINX partners are already considering for applying to the following Horizon Europe calls:

[DIGITAL-2022-CYBER-02-SUPPORTHEALTH Support to cybersecurity in the health sector](#)

[HORIZON-CL3-2022-CS-01-01 Improved monitoring of threats, intrusion detection and response in complex and heterogeneous digital systems and infrastructures](#)

Attracting investors

The SPHINX company can reach venture capital firms with the aim to find a partner to share the risk of the venture. A strategic decision can be taken to set up the firm in an EU city that could provide many opportunities due to the long list of venture capital firms in the area. VILABS has already made some preliminary discussions with some venture capitals presenting the SPHINX Toolkit and its business model.

6.5.1.2 Capital needs

The capital needs to develop a stable SPHINX prototype is estimated to approximately 1,150,000€. Let's assume that the average gross salary of a developer is 2,800€. For the 409PMs that are needed for all the components to reach TRL-7, this is translated to **1,145,200€**. A security budget equal to 20% of that budget has to be added to the calculated amount as is the usual practice of estimating budgets for ventures. Therefore, after adding the security budget the **total capital needs sum up to 1,375,000 €**.

6.5.2 Foundation stage

At this stage the company is established and gets ready to offer services to clients. The time length of the foundation stage is calculated to 2 months. The stage consists of several actions that are presented below:

Partners' agreement and articles of association

At first, the partners undertaking the investment analyse the requirements list and decide how (cash, staff, infrastructure) and in what extent each one of them contributes to the investment. The portion of shares of each partner is proportional to its contribution.

Next to the agreement of contributions, partners need to sign the articles of association. These are rules regarding the management of the company that shareholders and directors must agree to. The articles of association are necessary to found a company thus it is important to have them prepared. Another necessary decision that partners must take before the foundation of the company is the director in charge of running the company.

Office reservation

Right after the partners' agreement, the place which will host the company has to be reserved. The task of finding an office in a European city is assigned to a local real estate agency. It is assumed that it will take 1 month to sign the contract agreement and have the right to enter and use the office.

Foundation of the company

The formal procedures for setting up a business must be executed. In order to complete the foundation of a company, one shall provide the following information-documents and conduct the actions according to the corresponding governmental website:

- Provide name and address of the company
- Register with the Companies House
- Have at least 1 shareholder and 1 director
- Have articles of association
- Set up the company for Corporation Tax

6.5.3 Development stage

At this stage the company is established and gets ready to offer services to clients. The time length of the development stage is calculated to 4-6 months. The stage consists of several actions:

Infrastructure set up

Once the office is accessible, the necessary hardware is bought and installed in the office. At this point of time the company needs in total 5 servers to be used as workstations of testing and developing. The specifications of the hardware as well as the bandwidth needed will be evaluated at this point to reflect the latest technological state.

Staff recruitment

Given that the SPHINX Toolkit reached TRL-7 in the Preparation stage, the development phase demands 5 Full Time Employees (FTE) to fulfil the positions of:

- Senior software engineer (1),
- System administrator (1),
- Salesperson (1),
- Marketing (1) and
- Director (1).

The usual procedure of examining CVs is followed to select the most appropriate staff for each position. The recruiting process is assumed to take 2 months.

Partnerships establishment with relevant associations

At this early stage the SPHINX company initiates discussions with healthcare associations in order to become member, network and get visibility and credibility.

Follow up activities with SPHINX project contacts

The SPHINX company holds a list of potential clients which was filled through online and personal during the SPHINX project. The sales team uses them as its first entries in their Contact Management System and reach them for follow up activities.

6.5.4 Day to day operations

The SPHINX company consists of four units (marketing, sales, development and customer service) managed by the Director. The following figure demonstrates the organisational chart and then more details per unit follows.

Figure 5: Organisational chart

Marketing

The marketing team will be responsible for

- setting up and managing social media & networks
- organising workshops
- promoting the services in relevant conferences
- handling the company's website
- establish partnerships

Sales

The sales team works on the following tasks

- Contact management
- Sales process (negotiations, contracts, etc.)

Development

The development team is responsible for

- Testing and updating the SPHINX Toolkit
- Getting in touch with the component owners for developing new features for clients
- Installing the SPHINX Toolkit to HDOs

Customer service

The customer service team will have extended responsibilities in contrast to ordinary customer service departments. Its people will have the capabilities to execute the following tasks

- Setting up the SPHINX Toolkit to client's infrastructure
- Providing service support for any issues that might arise

6.6 SPHINX financial plan

The following tables of costs, income and operating result host estimations of important financial indicators that have been discussed within the consortium during an exploitation workshop that took place. These are preliminary figures but very close to reality.

Personnel costs

The following table shows the estimated personnel costs (internal and external) for a SPHINX company to operate.

Senior software engineer	10.200 €	10.200 €	10.200 €	10.200 €	10.200 €	10.200 €	10.200 €	10.200 €
System administrator	8.400 €	8.400 €	8.400 €	8.400 €	8.400 €	8.400 €	8.400 €	8.400 €
Senior business analyst	8.400 €	8.400 €	8.400 €	8.400 €	8.400 €	8.400 €	8.400 €	8.400 €
Marketing	8.400 €	8.400 €	8.400 €	8.400 €	8.400 €	8.400 €	8.400 €	8.400 €
Director	11.400 €	11.400 €	11.400 €	11.400 €	11.400 €	11.400 €	11.400 €	11.400 €
<i>Personnel (internal)</i>	<i>46.800 €</i>							
Accountant	800 €	450 €	450 €	450 €	450 €	450 €	450 €	450 €
Lawyer	1.000 €	450 €	450 €	450 €	450 €	450 €	450 €	450 €
<i>Outsourcing (external staff)</i>	<i>1.800 €</i>	<i>900 €</i>	<i>900 €</i>	<i>900 €</i>	<i>900 €</i>	<i>900 €</i>	<i>900 €</i>	<i>900 €</i>
Total payroll	48.600 €	47.700 €						

Table 5: Personnel costs

Sales forecast

The following table shows the sales forecast for every SPHINX service that will be offered (including maintenance).

		Q1-1	Q2-1	Q3-1	Q4-1	Q1-2	Q2-2	Q3-2	Q4-2	
1	Basic Service				1	1	1	1	1	2
2	Pro Service							1		1
3	Max Services							1		
4	Maintenance (Basic)							1	1	1
5	Maintenance (Pro)									
6	Maintenance (Max)									

Table 6: Sales forecast

	1.200.000 €								
		48.600 €	47.700 €	47.700 €	47.700 €	47.700 €	47.700 €	47.700 €	47.700 €
		20.000 €	0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €
		1.500 €	1.500 €	1.500 €	1.500 €	1.500 €	1.500 €	1.500 €	1.500 €
		650 €	650 €	650 €	650 €	650 €	650 €	650 €	650 €
		3.000 €	3.000 €	3.000 €	3.000 €	4.000 €	4.000 €	4.000 €	4.000 €
		0 €	9.600 €	9.600 €	9.600 €	26.720 €	34.720 €	26.720 €	21.120 €
		73.750 €	62.450 €	62.450 €	62.450 €	80.570 €	88.570 €	80.570 €	74.970 €
		Q1-1	Q2-1	Q3-1	Q4-1	Q1-2	Q2-2	Q3-2	Q4-2
ic Service		0 €	120.000 €	120.000 €	120.000 €	120.000 €	120.000 €	120.000 €	240.000 €
Service		0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €	190.000 €	0 €	190.000 €	0 €
k Services		0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €	290.000 €	0 €	0 €
aintenance (sic)		0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €	24.000 €	24.000 €	24.000 €	24.000 €
aintenance (Pro)		0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €
aintenance (ax)		0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €
arter Income		0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €
Q1-1		-1.200.000 €	120.000 €	120.000 €	120.000 €	334.000 €	434.000 €	334.000 €	264.000 €

Table 7: Financial plan per quarter

h flow									
umulated cash flow	73.750 €	62.450 €	62.450 €	62.450 €	80.570 €	88.570 €	80.570 €	74.970 €	
	-1.200.000 €	120.000 €	120.000 €	120.000 €	334.000 €	434.000 €	334.000 €	264.000 €	
	-1.273.750 €	57.550 €	57.550 €	57.550 €	253.430 €	345.430 €	253.430 €	189.030 €	
	-1.273.750 €	-1.216.200 €	-1.158.650 €	-1.101.100 €	-847.670 €	-502.240 €	-248.810 €	-59.780 €	

Table 8: Cash flow

Figure 6: Cash Flow

Figure 7: Accumulated cash flow

6.7 SWOT analysis

The SWOT analysis that follows summarises the strong and weak points of the SPHINX Toolkit against competing ones as well as opportunities and threats in the healthcare cybersecurity market.

Strengths	Weaknesses
<p>SPHINX Toolkit is vendor independent and protocol agnostic</p> <p>SPHINX can be tailored to the needs of the customers (customised services)</p> <p>SPHINX Toolkit is user friendly (end-user understanding through interactive dashboards)</p> <p>SPHINX Toolkit is interoperable with third party tools and services (SPHINX API for 3rd parties?)</p> <p>SPHINX Toolkit can automate tasks and increase performance</p>	<p>SPHINX Toolkit is composed of several components developed by different partners / different IPRs involved</p> <p>A lot of effort needed to reach a mature state</p> <p>Many different negotiations are needed with the component owners</p> <p>Large capital investment is needed</p> <p>Increased developing costs</p>
Opportunities	Threats

<p>Smart healthcare market expected to skyrocket in an increasingly complex cyber security environment</p> <p>Rising patient or user (e.g., doctor) concern on cybersecurity</p> <p>Open-source tools are being used for the development of the different components</p> <p>SPHINX Toolkit can be applied in different markets and application domains</p> <p>Market needs for low-cost usable security solutions</p>	<p>The competition is big and market operators and companies tend to rely on “brand name” software suppliers</p> <p>The lack of interoperability and poor standardisation in medical equipment/IoT/smart health infrastructure industry, raising barriers for wider market penetration</p> <p>Interoperability/integration failures both amongst SPHINX components and also with the third-party solutions</p>
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Table 9: Preliminary SPHINX SWOT analysis

7 Cybersecurity in healthcare Working Group

In order to make sure that the SPHINX knowledge will be sustained and widely exploited to European stakeholders and that appropriate actions will be made in order to explore the commercialization potential of the SPHINX Toolkit, we propose the development of a Working Group that will take up the results, will continue working in the SPHINX area and will focus on sustaining the SPHINX tools.

The “Cybersecurity in Healthcare” Working Group (in brief SPHINX WG) is a group of individuals (under the umbrella of the SPHINX project) that are interested - from a scientific and practical point of view - on the topics that were addressed by the SPHINX project throughout its whole duration.

It can be formed in an informal way, as a network of individuals, after the SPHINX project’s closure and consist initially of persons that have been actively involved in all the phases of SPHINX contributing to the project’s know-how.

The main aim of the Working Group is to capture the momentum that has been generated and exploit the project results on a voluntary basis while at the same time promote cybersecurity in healthcare IT infrastructures. SPHINX WG intends to:

- a) Disseminate the project’s results and findings to key stakeholders.
- b) Capitalise the outputs of the project and seek ways of exploiting and sustaining its legacies.
- c) Provide visibility to the persons involved in the project, as well as some kind of credibility in terms of their expertise on the topics addressed by the project.
- d) Sustain the regular contact and communication among its members towards future and further Research and Innovation activities relevant to the urban mobility.
- e) Organise meet ups in European countries to discuss about cybersecurity in health IT infrastructures.
- f) Organise training programmes, seminars and conferences addressed to healthcare professionals interested in gaining the necessary background information to improve cybersecurity in their organisations.

The specific objectives of the Working Group for the upcoming twelve months are:

- To discuss the possible composition of a SPHINX WG manifesto (declaration).
- To discuss the management structure of the WG.
- To organise (online or offline) Working Group meetings every four months that should run according to an announced agenda that is distributed well in advance of the meeting itself.
- To exploit the project results as these are presented in this document and in the respective SPHINX deliverables. This can be achieved by presenting the results of the pilot activities to various important events and to various key stakeholders.
- To continue discussions around the broad topic of cybersecurity in critical infrastructures. The working group will have a mailing list and a wiki where discussions around the SPHINX topics will take place.
- To keep the project’s website (<https://sphinx-project.eu>) active by posting relevant news items and informing about the Working Group’s activities. The target is to post at least 1 article per month. The names of the authors will be displayed in each post.
- To keep the project’s social media accounts (Twitter, Facebook) active by posting at least 2 times per month.
- To identify new research opportunities and collaboratively work on the preparation of research proposals in relation to the SPHINX.

- To discuss about adding new members to the working group. Experts can express their interest and the working group can discuss every six months and decide whether they should be included or not.
- To seek for sponsors that will provide financial support to the Working Group.

The SPHINX WP could include in next phases of its existence, other individuals that were not involved in the SPHINX project. This way, it could be established either formally or informally as a broader open network.

The main dissemination tools of the SPHINX WG will be the project's website and the project's social media accounts (Facebook, Twitter and LinkedIn).

The specific timeline for next major activities of the WG include the following:

1. The Working Group is being setup. The members and their CVs are ready and included in the project's website. (Deadline: June 2022).
2. The Working Group manifesto is ready (Deadline: September 2022).
3. The Working Group website is ready. The website will be restructured to accommodate the Working Group needs but the content that is already there will still exist (Deadline: September 2022).
4. Wide online and offline dissemination campaign will take place informing about the establishment of the Working Group. A press release will be created and will be sent to relevant contacts. Our aim is to inform stakeholders about our activities. (Deadline: October 2022).
5. Wide online and offline dissemination campaign of the SPHINX tools will take place (Deadline: October 2022).
6. The Working Group has a management structure that has been agreed by all members. Roles are being allocated to members (Deadline: November 2022)

Figure 8: Timeline for important WG activities

8 Towards the sustainability of the SPHINX project

SPHINX project delivered an IT solution, tested, and evaluated in four different health delivery originations in three European countries (Greece, Portugal and Romania).

In parallel with the exploitation actions, this deliverable takes into account the sustainability element for the overall plan of impact maximization in order to secure that the project results will remain active and even further expanded, beyond the contractual project end. Therefore, the sustainability of SPHINX envisions four key options:

Pilot organisations to maintain the SPHINX Toolkit. During the project progress, the four project pilot sites (General Hospital of Volos (Greece), University Hospital of Larissa (Greece), Hospital do Espírito Santo de Évora (Portugal), and Polaris Medical Hospital (Romania)) demonstrated the SPHINX Toolkit in a replicated/emulated real environment but with no real patient data. After the completion of the project, the platform TRL will be increased but not ready to enter the market with real patient data. Given the willingness of pilot partners to further provide parts of their infrastructures as testbeds for SPHINX's development, a partnership could be created consisting of some SPHINX partners to work in order to find further funding (e.g., other funding opportunities) and proceed with advancing the platform development in collaboration with the involved pilots.

New Health Delivery Organisations to replicate the SPHINX Toolkit. SPHINX is designed in a scalable manner in order to be used by different IT infrastructures existing in hospitals across Europe. The steps that project pilots followed to deploy the platform can be utilised to generate replication plans that any healthcare and medical organisation could follow to deploy SPHINX platform. Collaboration agreements between the HDOs and the technical partners are purposeful for such possibility.

To verify the business potential of the SPHINX Toolkit. The business plan is developed during the project to facilitate the commercial exploitation of the Toolkit. This plan needs to be further evaluated by stakeholders from the targeted market, to conclude on a mature plan of high potential. Project partners will agree on a partnership that includes investigation for further funding, to develop this RIA result into a product ready to enter the market. The establishment of the SPHINX working group could potentially boost these activities.

To proceed with the further usage of individual exploitable results. Industrial (for-profit) partners envisage to include the individual components at their portfolios. The expertise and technological know-how gained within the SPHINX project duration can become an asset for each partner's businesses. In this respect, stand-alone and/or bilateral solutions developed will be offered by technical partners as parts of their expert services.

9 Conclusions

D8.10 presented the final version of the SPHINX exploitation and sustainability plan. At first, the document presented the main SPHINX exploitable results along with a summary of their exploitation goals for these outputs (Chapters 2 & 3). Then, the deliverable analysed the exploitation and sustainability options of SPHINX partners as they have been identified through a 2-round internal survey (Chapter 4). It then elaborated on a plan for identifying the SPHINX business models and its business plan (Chapters 5 & 6). Finally, the deliverable concluded with Chapter 7 as an outline for a cybersecurity working group that will comprise SPHINX partners and will work towards the exploitation and sustainability of the project's results. Consequently, the sustainability aspect has been addressed in four key perspectives in Chapter 8.

The scope of the final SPHINX Exploitation, Sustainability and Business Plans (D8.10) was present a consolidated view of the SPHINX exploitation options, as these were defined by the consortium, and define actions necessary for the commercialisation of the SPHINX Toolkit.

10 References

1. Strategyzer (2020). *The Business Model Canvas*. Available at: <https://www.strategyzer.com/canvas/business-model-canvas>
2. World Intellectual Property Organisation (2022). *What is Intellectual Property?* Available at: <https://www.wipo.int/about-ip/en/>

Appendix I: SPHINX exploitation questionnaire v1

Dear colleague,

Please spend a few minutes answering this questionnaire.

This questionnaire is SPHINX consortium's tool to collect information concerning all partners' strategy to exploit the SPHINX project outcomes both at individual level and at the level of the consortium as a whole. It will also serve the consortium to analyse your ideas and opinions about the exploitation prospects of the SPHINX project.

Your answers will be analysed, synthesized and included in deliverable D8.10 "Exploitation, Sustainability and Business Plans v2". This RAPP Project Exploitation plan is requested by the European Commission to assess the viability of the project after its completion.

Thank you for being analytical and specific while providing all thoughts and ideas.

Key concepts:

EXPLOITATION PLANS

The European Commission pays great attention to the project's measures to maximize the impact of the results on science, technology and society. Precisely, ensuring that project outcomes are widely "disseminated" beyond the partners' audience as well as effectively "exploited" guarantees the utility of the results after the project and, therefore, it is the source of accountability of projects funded by taxpayers' money.

To develop an Exploitation Plan is a systematic requirement for EU-funded projects, which should detail how the individual project partners and the consortium as a whole intend to make use of the research results, with the aim of taking advantage of all activities in the project. While some partners will only foresee an improvement of their expertise, or level of publications; others might envision concrete exploitation perspectives based on more or less formalised business models. **Part 1** of the present questionnaire focuses on exploitation plans at each partner's level. **Part 2** is devoted to gather ideas and opinions from partners about how the global exploitation plan should be implemented by the consortium.

SUSTAINABILITY

The European Commission envisages the funding of research projects as a previous step in the development of a more ambitious path by part of or all consortium partners, in such a way that research outcomes lead to a pre-commercial or commercial phase where no EU funding is necessary, and where consortium partners have found a way, often through business models, to ensure continuity of the project efforts beyond the overall project lifecycle.

Precisely, as far as consortium partners are co-investing in the project's research, they are expected to have similar interests to exploit project outcomes, thus ensuring the sustainability of their project. A credible "sustainability plan" is one of the most valuable outputs of the project.

Please indicate in the below table the name(s) of the representative(s) of your organisation providing answers to this questionnaire. Several representatives from your organisation may usefully fill in this questionnaire in order to provide the consortium with a better understanding of the way your organisation foresees the exploitation and sustainability of the project

	Contributor 1	Contributor 2	Contributor 3
Full name			

Organization			
Position			
Email address			

Part 1: Exploitation plans at your organisation's level

Q1. What did your organization achieve by getting involved in the SPHINX project? (Increase of your expertise in x domain, knowledge acquisition, network enhancement, commercial opportunities, scientific/ technological advances, etc.)

Q2. Which of the SPHINX outcomes is your organisation planning to exploit?

Q3. How does your organisation plan to exploit the SPHINX outcomes after the project?

Part 2: "Towards the sustainability of the RAPP Joint Initiative"

Q4. If your organisation was to be involved in a joint initiative for the exploitation of the SPHINX project, which of the above business models would better fit its needs? Please provide your comments, remarks, on the selected business models:

Q5. What, in your opinion, are the key SPHINX developments and measures necessary to successfully apply the selected business model?

Q6. What, in your opinion, are the main obstacles faced by the RAPP partnership towards the implementation of the business models?

Q7. Do you have any recommendations regarding the proposed RAPP business models? Do you have other exploitation ideas that are not satisfied by the proposed business models?

Many thanks for finishing this survey - your feedback is sincerely appreciated!

Appendix II: SPHINX exploitation questionnaire v2

Dear colleague,

Please spend a few minutes answering this questionnaire.

This questionnaire is SPHINX consortium's tool to collect information concerning all partners' strategy to exploit the SPHINX project outcomes both at individual level and at the level of the consortium as a whole. It will also serve the consortium to analyse your ideas and opinions about the exploitation prospects of the SPHINX project and the components that have been developed.

Your answers will be analysed, synthesized and included in deliverable "D8.10 Exploitation, Sustainability and Business Plans v3".

Thank you for being analytical and specific while providing all thoughts and ideas.

Key concepts:

EXPLOITATION

The European Commission pays great attention to the project's measures to maximize the impact of the results on science, technology and society. Precisely, ensuring that project outcomes are widely "disseminated" beyond the partners' audience as well as effectively "exploited" guarantees the utility of the results after the project and, therefore, it is the source of accountability of projects funded by taxpayers' money.

To develop an Exploitation Plan is a systematic requirement for EU-funded projects, which should detail how the individual project partners and the consortium as a whole intend to make use of the research results, with the aim of taking advantage of all activities in the project.

SUSTAINABILITY

The European Commission envisages the funding of research projects as a previous step in the development of a more ambitious path by part of or all consortium partners, in such a way that research outcomes lead to a pre-commercial or commercial phase where no EU funding is necessary, and where consortium partners have found a way, often through business models, to ensure continuity of the project efforts beyond the overall project lifecycle.

Precisely, as far as consortium partners are co-investing in the project's research, they are expected to have similar interests to exploit project outcomes, thus ensuring the sustainability of their project.

Please indicate in the below table the name(s) of the representative(s) of your organisation providing answers to this questionnaire. Several representatives from your organisation may usefully fill in this questionnaire in order to provide the consortium with a better understanding of the way your organisation foresees the exploitation and sustainability of the project

	Contributor 1	Contributor 2	Contributor 3
Full name			
Organization			
Email address			

Q1. How did your organisation benefit by participating in the SPHINX project? (*Increase of your expertise in x domain, knowledge acquisition, network enhancement, commercial opportunities, scientific/ technological advances, etc.*)

Q2. Please describe, in a concrete and comprehensive manner, which of the project outputs is your organization planning to exploit, and how? (*e.g. SPHINX Toolkit, SPHINX components, SPHINX pilot results, SPHINX policies, best practices and lessons learned, Scientific knowledge, other?*) / (*e.g. scientific publications, open source repository, demo videos, standardization activities, policy briefs, best practices, training materials, technical reports, interviews, synergies, PhDs, academic modules, new products and services etc.*)

Q2.1 For each of the project outcomes mentioned above please complete the following Table.

Name of the component: XXX	
Short description of the component	
Briefly list the potential customers that would be willing to use the component	
Are you aware of any competitors that offer similar solutions?	
Briefly describe the value of the component (why it is different than other solutions?)	
TRL of the component at the end of the project	(on p.99 of the SPHINX GA you can find the TRL we promised)
Estimate the development needed to reach TRL 7	XX PMs
Are you planning to offer commercial services for this component?	(if yes, please elaborate)
How much would you charge for the component (provided that it reaches TRL 7) (if you intend to offer it as open source please state the open source license under which you are planning to release it and whether it will be already available on an open repository by the end of the project)	(on p.119 of the SPHINX GA you can find a table with the prices we initially proposed)

Q4. Would your organisation be willing to be involved in a joint initiative for the exploitation and sustainability of the SPHINX Toolkit after the end of the project? *(Please provide your comments and remarks)*

Q5. What, in your opinion, are the key actions necessary to successfully exploit and sustain the SPHINX Toolkit after the end of the project?

Q6. What, in your opinion, are the main obstacles towards successfully exploiting and sustaining the SPHINX Toolkit after the end of the project?

If you have further comments / recommendations, please write them here.

Many thanks for finishing this survey - your feedback is sincerely appreciated!

